

Is – Is not – Does – Does not

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

A concise and effective method for **defining role responsibilities** within the team. Through this activity, participants explore both positive and negative aspects of the role, clarifying its functions and limitations.

Benefits

This focused approach enhances consensual understanding of the scope and boundaries associated with specific roles, promotes collaboration, and facilitates strategic decision-making.

Practical recommendations

1. Divide a white canvas in four areas (Is / Is Not / Does / Does Not).
2. Write the name of the role (e.g. WP leader, coordinator,...) you are discussing above the quadrants.
3. Ask each participant to describe the role on sticky notes and put them on the correspondent areas.
4. Read and group the similar notes.
5. Consider repeating for another team role.
6. Place the conclusions somewhere they can be consulted throughout the project proposal writing phase and refined when the project gets granted.

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Transparent communication about agenda's, expectations, and results

The recognition of, and work with, the limitations of different organisations

Being comfortable with co-ownership and responsibility of tasks, results, and outcomes

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)

[Link to 'Is-is not- does - does not' by FunRetrospectives](#)

Figure: Poster layout (source: FunRetrospectives)

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